

AYURVEDIC MANAGEMENT OF KITIBH KUSHTA (PSORIASIS)**Dr. Ruchita Sakharam Pashte*¹, Dr. Amit Chavan²**

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ABSTRACT

People suffering from autoimmune disease is increasing day by day. The exact cause of the autoimmune disease is still unknown. Usually 10-15 % cases present before general practitioners are pertaining to skin disease. Due to altered lifestyle, lack of physical exercise, unhygienic, mental stress, over eating, nutrition deficiency, skin disease are commonly observed. Psoriasis is one of them and it is a chronic disorder. Dry thick raised itchy patches on skin are the sign of psoriasis. It is triggered by infection, stress, cold and a sedentary lifestyle. There is no known cure, but with proper management, serious flares can be avoided. Such disease can be effectively managed by ayurveda. All the skin diseases in ayurveda have been discussed under the broad heading of Kushta which is further divided into Mahakushta and Kshudra Kushta. This paper highlights a case study of kitibh kushta treated with ayurvedic principles in particular shodhan chikitsa.

KEYWORDS: Kitibh kushta, vaman karma, virechan karm.

INTRODUCTION

Psoriasis is considered as a genetic, immunological, systemic disorder.^{[1][2]} With prevalence of 1-3% and its socioeconomic impact is remarkable.^[3] Hence it is the need of the day to find managing techniques for such widely occurring disease. There is no such cure as of now which completely cures psoriasis. Steroids and immunosuppressants temporarily manage the symptoms but exposure to triggering factors, it flares up. However, it can be effectively

managed with the help of Ayurveda.

Lifestyle modification is also necessary along with ayurveda treatment. ayurveda focuses on treating the root cause of disease instead of just managing the symptoms.

As per ayurveda symptoms of psoriasis can be compared to that of Kitibha kushta.

Kitibha kushta lakshane: श्यावं किणखरस्पर्शं परुषं किकिभं मतम् ॥ च.चच.7/21

It is the vaat kaph dominant skin disease.

BRIEF HISTORY OF PATIENT

A 34 year old male who was apparently normal before 4-5 years, developed small skin lesions over lower limb and scalp associated with severe itching and powdery discharge and very dry skin.

He is a businessman working with wooden box material belonging to high socioeconomic class, hindu family background. He consulted all local allopathic physicians before but he couldn't get any relief from the symptoms, later he consulted our hospital OPD for treatment. He is non- diabetic, non- hypertensive. Having a habit of eating spicy food, junk food, intake of non vegetarian trice in a week, consumption of alcohol occasionally.^[4]

CLINICAL FINDING

LOCAL EXAMINATION

1. Whitish pink scale on the lower limb and scalp.
2. Severe itching
3. Powdery discharge
4. Dry, rough lesion.

Laboratory investigation

Blood routine: normal Ecg: normal

SAMPRAPTI GHATAK

Dosh - Tridosh [kaphpradhan vaat] Dushya - Twak, Rakta, Mansa, Lasika Agni - Jatharagni mandya

Srotas - Rasavaha, Raktavaha Srotodrushti prakar - Sanga Rogmarga - Bahya

Udhbava sthana - Amashaya Vyaktasthana - Twacha

SAMPRAPTI^[5]

Nidan sevana like Aharaja-Viharaja-Manasika

(Spicy foods, junk foods, exposure to cold air, consumption of alcohol, non-vegetarian diet)

Tridosha + Twak, Rakta, Mamsa, Lasika

Sthanasamshraya in Twacha

Pidika with Kandu, Daha all over the body

Kitibha kushta

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Treatment Plan^[6]

1. Aampachan
2. Snehapana
3. Vaman karma
4. Virechan karma
5. Pathya -Apathya palan

Date	Treatment	Procedure/Medicine
4/4/2023 - 8/04/2023	Amapachana	Pravalpanchamrut vati 2bd , shankh vati 2bd, aampachak vati 2bd with water after food for 5 days.
9/04/2023 - 15/04/2023	snehapana	Vajrak ghrita ^[7] - 30 ml 1st day 60 ml 2nd day 90ml 3rd day 120 ml 4th day 150ml 5th day 180 ml 6th day 210 ml 7th day
16/04/2023	Sarvang snehan swedan and also given kaphautkleshita ahar	777 oil + psorolin oil followed by mridu nadi sweda
17/04/2023	Sarvang snehan swedana followed by vaman karma	Yavagupana given at 7am After that aakanthpana with milk. Vamak yog given ^[8] : 130ml

		[madhu 30ml+ saindhav 10gm+ madanphal phant 90ml]
	Shudhi lakshanes ^[9] : madhyam shuddhi	Aantriki :pittant Vaigiki : 6 vega Laingiki : samyak vaman lakshane
17/04/2023- 21/04/2023	Sansarjan kram given ^[10]	5 days for madhyama sudhi
22/04/2023- 26/04/2023	aampachana	Pravalpanchamrut vati 2bd, shankha vati 2bd, aampachak vati given with water after food for 5 days
27/04/2023- 03/05/2023	Snehapana	Vajraka ghrita 40ml 1st day 80ml 2nd day
		120 ml 3rd day 160ml 4th day 200ml 5th day 240ml 6th day 280 ml 7th day
04/05/2023- 05/05/2023	Sarvanga snehana with swedana	777 oil + psorolin oil
06/05/2023	Virechana karma	Manibhadragud avaleh ^[11] 50 gm morning 8 am and given abhayadi modak tab 1 at 8:30am
	Parikshan : madhyam shuddhi Sansarjan kram given for 5 days	Vaigiki priksha : 20 veg Aantriki patiksha : kaphant Laingiki pariksha : samyak yog lakshane

PATHYA AND APATHYA

PATHYA = laghu ahar, aamla -lavan-katu aalp praman, muga

Apathya = tila tail, dhadhi, madhya, mamsa, mastya sevana, vegadharana, adhika vyayama.

FEATURES	BEFORE TREATMENT	AFTER VAMANA KARMA	AFTER VIRECHANA KARMA
colour	Silvery	Mild reduce	reduce
Itching	severe	mild	absent
Lesion size	Big and larger	Mild reduce	absent
Lesion no	more	decreased	decreased
PASI score	9.3	4.2	2.1
Scaling	present	Moderately present	absent

Sign and symptoms	Before treatment	After vaman	After virechana
Shyava varna	+++	+	-
Kin khar sparsham	+++	++	-
parusham	+++	+	-
kandu	+++	+	-

Probable mode of action

Amapachan dravya helps in maintenance of agni and do agni sandeepana karma.

Both snehana and swedana help in the movement of dosha and dosha shithilikarana and bring doshas from shakhas to koshta.

Vaman aids in the removal of the koshtas vitiated doshas, primarily kapha and pitta.

The ushan, tikshna, vyavayi and vikasi guna characteristics of vamanopaga dravyas such as madanphal churna, saindhav, madhu, and yashimadhu phanta increase absorption rate and aid in reaching hriday. It travels to dhamani from hriday and reaches all sthula and sukshma

strotas there. In vama dravyas the agni and vayu mahabhutas are more prevalent. As a result, it possesses the urdhwabhagahar prabhav, which causes the doshas to be expelled from the mouth in an upward direction.

The virechan dravya spreads throughout the body in cellular level due to its pharmacological properties. Vyavayi property of virechan dravya is responsible for quick absorption, while vikasi guna causes softening and loosening of the bond by dhatu shathilyakaran.

Due to ushan guna dosha sangata is liquefied. Tikshana guna of virechan dravya produce chedan of dosha which are already softened due to snehan and swedana so liquefied dosha is dragged to koshta and eliminated from the body.

DISCUSSION

Patient had an habit of irregular food intake and other nidanas like madhya sevana, mamsa sevana, adhika vyayama, ratrijagaran, adhik chinta leads to kitibh kushta.

Depending on the lakshans and nidanas according to kushta chikitsa planned treatment by ayurvedic management like Deepana, Pachana, Vamana, Virechana were given.

CONCLUSION

In the present case depending on nidana and lakshana it was diagnosed as kitibha kushta. This case study is documented evidence for the successful management of kitibha kushta by kushta chikitsasutra.

Vaman and virechan are the procedures one can practise comfortably and expect good response in kitibha kushta and also skin manifestation.

Along with proper following, pathya will give faster and long lasting results.

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